

WEBVR - MAKING EDUCATIONAL CONTENT A PUBLIC EXPERIENCE

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Indexing of geocoded educational content

In the following, we will explain how educational content on the topic of local environmental challenges can be prepared with the use of a web content index to allow for international participation. A human being wants to interact with their environment anywhere on Earth. What aid is available to them? The retrieval of information about an individual's geolocation could be supported by an open quality assured and geocoded Web Index. Indexing openly available educational content in such a Web Index would pave the way for international capacity building.

Real-World Laboratory Queichland

Real-world laboratories are becoming increasingly popular in research on sustainability and transformation [1]. However, this type of education has so far been regarded as a marginal aspect of real laboratories [2]. As educational venues, however, they represent an ideal foundation for education of sustainable development in an authentic learning environment [3]. In the Queichland Real-World Laboratory, authentic learning concepts on environment-related contexts are developed and offered in a dialogue between science, educational institutions and civil society. These offerings enable problem-oriented and active development of research-based knowledge about environmental processes. The contents refer to three Sustainable Development Goals 6 ("Clean Water and Sanitation"), 13 ("ClimateAction") and 15 ("Life on Land"). With a strong focus on digital educational and participation opportunities, the use of virtual reality (VR) as a publicly accessible educational tool is also being investigated. The Real-World Laboratory Queichland offers its services in the Queichpark, which has a green surface area of about 7 hectares in Landau, Germany (Palatinate).

Virtual reality as an educational offer

VR has been in focus for quite some time as a new, powerful medium for digital educational opportunities. During the presence experience, cognitive and mental capacities are used to fade out the real environment in order to completely immerse oneself into the world created by the medium. One experiences the feeling of presence in the space conveyed by the medium. For VR the focus is on the so-called spatial presence experience. Here the medium used disappears from the user's perception and he/she feels present in the environment presented to him/her [4]. Modern technology creates better coverage of the perception system with constantly increasing graphics performance, improved sound quality and the inclusion of additional senses to enable spatial presence experiences.

In the Real-World Laboratory Queichland this technology is used to embed an experiment on water treatment with seeds of *Moringa Oleifera* in school and extracurricular educational contexts. By using VR the context can be made more authentic. By simulating environmental scenarios, the student can perceive the authenticity of the problem more realistically and experience the context of the problem and the necessity of the corresponding SDG 6 more "realistically".

WebVR for public access to education

In contrast to native apps, WebVR offers many advantages in the area of public accessibility. By supporting the WebVR API of various browsers it is possible to access VR content via desktop PCs, smartphones and head-mounted displays (HMDs) directly as a web app in the browser. This universal access makes it possible to make VR content available across different media. With the open source framework, Aframe, WebVR can be accessed and displayed in supporting browsers (e.g. Chrome and Firefox). With the help of the cross-browser JavaScript 3D Library Three.js, WebGL renders the necessary 3D representations and animations directly in the browser. By using JavaScript and HTML5, all functions can be easily displayed and executed across different media. When designing the VR environment, it must be taken into account which end device is to be the focus of use.

In the Real-World Laboratory Queichland, we are investigating how educational offers of the authentic learning location can be implemented as a WebVR app for use by the general population as well as school classrooms. The transferability to a possible international level is one of the main topics.

Conclusion

Educational geolocated VR content could be integrated as a micro service into an Open Web Index (OWI). Through an analysis of the quality of the content and the state of the art by scientists, these applications can then be indexed and provided with a digital signature of the respective institution. The OWI then enables the integration of the micro service into the search results through specific search queries. By using VR content at specific locations, interaction with the environment can be enhanced and local capacity building can be achieved.

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